

Connecting the dots in TVET in Cambodia: Stakeholders and their collaboration

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Cambodia #3 (2023)

At a glance

Collaboration between training providers and the industry is crucial for a responsive technical and vocational education and training (TVET) system. It not only alleviates the skill mismatch problem but also contributes to better quality training provision and increases the employability of TVET graduates. Based on the findings from the “Skills for Industry” research project conducted from 2017 to 2023 in Cambodia and five other countries, training providers and the industry in Cambodia have collaborated in many forms and through formal and informal means. However, such collaborations are constrained because of four limitations: (1) low technical capacity of many training providers and instructors; (2) limited financial resources; (3) an absence of a coordinating mechanism; and (4) the lack of an enabling environment. In an attempt to address these issues, this policy brief recommends the following:

- Improving training provider capacity and private sector participation in collaboration through the strengthening of training institution credibility and the use of benefit and cost-sharing mechanisms.
- Establishing an integrated coordination mechanism using a multi-stakeholder approach, specifying and activating stakeholders’ roles and responsibilities, to achieve a more sustained collaboration.

- Enforcing collaboration with full technical and financial support from government bodies and key stakeholders in TVET to improve the enabling environment for implementing collaboration.

Introduction

Skill development is fundamental in pushing for industrial growth and economic development. TVET plays an important role in this aspect, for instance, by increasing labor productivity and reducing poverty (Asian Development Bank 2009). As evidenced in various national policies such as the National Employment Policy 2015–2025 and the National TVET Policy 2017–2025, establishing a TVET system that is recognized internationally and responsive to market demand is a priority for the Royal Government of Cambodia (Royal Government of Cambodia 2015; Ministry of Labor and Vocational Training 2017). Yet, realizing such a priority is challenging due to many factors. One of them is the lack of effective collaboration among stakeholders in the TVET sector, particularly, the collaboration between training providers and the industry.

Against such a backdrop, this policy brief discusses the underlying collaboration challenges in the Cambodian TVET sector. This policy brief looks at the collaborations between training providers and the private sector by using interview data from the second phase of the “Skills for Industry” project, conducted either in-person or virtually between March and July 2022, with representatives from nine Cambodian government bodies (GB), 20 training providers (TP), four industry associations (IA), and three labor unions (LU).

Collaborations are crucially important for skill provision in response to labor market demand

It is extremely important that training providers and the industry collaborate. Their collaboration is needed for improving the quality of skill training programs, increasing their industrial relevance and therefore employability of graduates, and making an overall contribution to the establishment of an inclusive and effective skill development system. Respondents elaborated on this below:

“Yes, importantly, it is related to new technologies when we sign an MOU with foreign companies, we can upgrade our trainers’ capacity and our knowledge with their modern technical tools that we have never used.” – TPO5

“So, we coordinate the validation workshop, consultation workshop, technical input for competence standard, and curriculum-based development to ensure that the training institutes’ technical information responds to the private sector’s needs. So, we call industry specialists; we work directly with industry specialists and teachers from training institutes to develop the curriculum and standard competency for high diploma programs.” – IA32

“Because whenever we adjust our curriculum, we need to invite them (private sector) to discuss their current and long-term demands in order for us to set the right direction that matches the job opportunities.” – GB21

Collaborations happen but insufficiently and informally

The most common forms of collaboration reported by most training providers include student internships, employment opportunities, study visits and knowledge sharing. Although less reported, collaborations also took place during curriculum development and improvement of training facility

and equipment by training providers, which often involves the transfer of technology and the provision of training facilities to bolster the practical aspects of the curriculum. Such collaborations happened based on more informal than formal bases. TVET institutions that do not have a formal basis for collaborations often collaborate through personal connections, which are often fragile, sporadic and ad hoc.

“There are students who are employed at some companies, we can ask for the administrative number and make a proposal to their chairman or director and give them a visit.” – TP10

“We do have some collaboration but not a lot... But some of the lecturers have connections with private companies. They could use that connection and allow our students to do an internship there.” – TPO8

On a formal basis, collaborations happened through MOUs (Memorandum of Understanding) or official agreements with companies where both parties agree on their written roles and responsibilities. However, according to the respondents from training providers TPO7 and TPO6, the formality seems to not really determine the effectiveness of the collaboration that takes place at this level, although sometimes it does provide a space for collaborations at a deeper level.

“Personally, the agreement is just a piece of paper... But relationships result from a deep understanding between the school and companies, which is a necessary thing.” – TPO7

“We used to have signed MOUs with various firms, but most of them were not so active. We, therefore, eliminated them from our network.” – TPO6

“Then we drafted an MoU or MoA. In that instrument, we bound each other about the level of cooperation such as whether our lecturers can go to their factories or support any program. That is a strong document that leads to fruitful results.” – TP15

As mentioned above, collaborations take many forms but are not systematically integrated. Without a systematic and well-integrated coordinating mechanism, collaborations remain shallow and ad hoc, and it would still be a challenge to implement them effectively. In this respect, one respondent pointed out:

“They need to build a team and a document [refers to policy or regulation]. To be honest, we already have those documents; we just lack mechanisms such as discussion, facilitation, meeting arrangement, etc.” – GB22

Training providers struggle to provide industry- or skill-specific training programs due to limited capacity, hindering their collaboration with companies

Most training institutions acknowledged constraints on technical resources from their side. In their view, the lack of qualified trainers, training equipment and facilities has hindered their collaborations with the private sector, meaning that they could not offer training courses that would meet the expectations of the private sector. The lack of such technical resources and capacity is often intertwined with the poor quality of skill provision, probably making companies reluctant to collaborate with training providers. Two training providers illustrated their struggle:

“They may need a food quality analyst or they ask us to analyse their food while we cannot offer them such an analysis. Therefore, they need to look elsewhere or abroad. After we don’t have this capability for a few years, they wouldn’t wait for us.” – TP16

“For the internal factors, in engineering, there are limited human resources. We have to admit that students and lecturers in engineering fields are limited.” – TP01

It is usually hard to implement multi-stakeholder collaborations with limited financial resources

The government, training institutions and industry associations do not have sufficient financial packages to implement their activities in general, not to mention collaboration activities, in particular. Moreover, the private sector is reluctant to invest its financial resources as profit-oriented organizations, considering the uncertainty about returns from investment in collaboration.

“Our development partners have also provided a lot of funding, such as ADB, who is a key player here. But the stakeholder that we [respondent’s organization] have not been able to leverage a lot of funds is the private sector.” – GB26

“We cannot invite them because we don’t have the budget to cover them.” – TP09

“Again, for our organization, we can’t do much, and we have limited resources, as well.” – IA32

There is also no sustainable collaborative funding mechanism, where financial resources from all stakeholders are pooled together for collaboration as pointed out by TP07 below.

“So far there has been no one except for the government which provides the funding source but it would be better if the government had a mechanism to encourage private companies to support the funding.” – TP07

The lack of commitment and effective policy implementation has negatively affected the enabling environment for implementing collaboration

Not all firms are willing and committed to collaborating with training providers. Their reluctance may be a result of the uncertainties about returns on investment in collaborations with training providers, and at other times, a lack of awareness about existing collaboration mechanisms, suggesting a lack of information dissemination and understanding of the benefits of collaborations with TVET institutions.

“Because we will just waste our money, our time, and our resources when we’re conducting the training that is so-so. We have to really make sure that the training that we provide, the learning and development that we provide, would really result in something that is positive, which enhances the skills and ultimately helps the companies’ productivity in terms of their production.” – IA32

“For the short-term mission [refers to government effort in getting private sector to collaborate with training providers], we need [more] time for the industry to see the advantage of skill training for their labour.” – GB26

“It’s not easy to convince the private institutions to participate, we need to make them understand about the process and the success of the training outcomes that contributes to their success, as well.” – GB21

Despite the existence of numerous key policies and regulations regarding collaboration with the private sector, the implementation falls short. Nonetheless, it is expected that the government should be a key actor in making these collaborations work as the labor union of LU35 expressed below.

“Building trust takes a lot, so the private sector or companies should discuss this with the government first. After that, the government can talk with the workers’ representatives about the demand in the job market.” – LU35

Collaboration requires a bridging step from every stakeholder and it starts from trust

As commonly perceived by all stakeholders, effective collaboration is one that would yield mutual benefits and is made up of involvement from training providers, government bodies and the private sector.

“In my opinion, a robust partnership would effectively harmonize the firm and TVET school together because they can maximize their mutual interest.” – TPO6

Each stakeholder needs to do what they do best. Training providers provide quality training that meets industrial demand, as mentioned by TP16. The private sector takes part in ensuring the delivery of industry- or skill-specific training through sharing of technical expertise, technology, and financial resources. The government can facilitate and support the implementation of such collaborations by providing financial support and establishing various channels and platforms, both physically and digitally, for the industry and training providers to connect with each other for collaborations.

“We already know these challenges and we start to equip more modern equipment for analysis. Next year, we could analyse more and we will start to cooperate with them. Our previous collaboration is based on our capability to address their need.” – TP16

“They lack partners and a network with good schools. So, SDF (Skills Development Fund) does not only provide money, but also the network and good schools.” – GB26

Connecting all the dots in TVET

All respondents generally value collaborations. Various approaches, ranging from the use of personal connections to making use of formal collaboration agreements, are implemented. However, collaborations are still challenged by limited technical capacity and financial resources, the lack of an integrated coordinating mechanism, and the unfavorable environment caused by the wavering commitment and policy implementation.

To address these challenges, it would need viable solutions that consider all fronts:

- **Strengthening training provider capacity and credibility:**

It is vital to improve the capacity of training providers as well as instructors in delivering relevant and effective training programs to increase their credibility for collaboration. In the long run, this can be done through trainers' upskilling and development of an industry-relevant training curriculum based on a comprehensive skills-need information system through regular labor market analysis and forecasting.

- **Ensuring cost and benefit sharing in collaboration:**

The private sector's involvement in collaborations must be encouraged by using benefit assurance and cost-sharing mechanisms. Leveraging existing co-financing schemes, such as a Trust Fund for skills training could be one way to achieve this goal. The implementation of the Skill Development Fund program is also a good example, where the government grants

partial funding to approved training programs requested by the private sector and provided by training institutions. Furthermore, there would need to be effective measures in place to ensure the proper implementation and effective utilization of the funding scheme for skill development.

- **Sustaining collaboration using a systematic and integrated approach:**

Using collaborative funding, an integrated collaborative system needs to be established with a clear mandate for the involvement of each stakeholder to ensure regular and sustained collaboration. For instance, there should be a set of national guidelines that direct companies and training providers in terms of collaboration. The guidelines should detail the contribution that each stakeholder must make as well as the expected benefits that would accrue from such a collaboration. Coordination of this collaborative system should adhere to a multi-stakeholder approach, where each stakeholder takes part in managing and implementing the collaboration. A modality akin to the public-private partnership (PPP) could be a good approach to achieve this.

- **Enforcing existing policies and regulations for collaboration:**

Enforcing and fully supporting the implementation of existing policies and regulations that encourage collaboration in terms of both technical and financial support would be another important step. In the TVET Policy 2017-2025, enhancing PPP in the TVET system was noted as one of the government strategies in promoting resource pooling to support skill development, especially in the development of responsive training programs. The establishment of the Skill Development Fund is another prime example of government initiatives that attempt to invoke systematic collaboration at the national level. With such measures, an enabling environment for the implementation of collaboration activities could be established.

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